

Branch ^a	Corrected p-value ^b	ω^{+c}	Pr [$\omega=\omega^{+}$] ^d
<i>D.labrax ogn1</i>	<0.0001	74.07	0.16
<i>T.rubripes ogn1</i>	0.000	16.40	0.15
<i>O.latipes ogn1</i>	0.001	11.39	0.20
<i>O.niloticus ogn1</i>	0.003	21.47	0.07
Node 15 ^e	0.011	863.89	0.04
<i>C. picta belii ogn1</i>	0.020	2785.35	0.02
<i>A.mexicanus ogn1</i>	0.030	654.36	0.09
<i>L.chalumnae ogn1</i>	0.043	12.91	0.19

^a Branch under episodic diversifying selection at $p \leq 0.05$.

^b The p-value for episodic selection at this branch corrected for multiple testing using the Holm-Bonferroni method

^c The ω value inferred for positively selected sites long this branch.

^d The proportion of sites inferred to be evolving at ω^{+} along this branch.

^e Node 15 refers to the separation of *Takifugu rubripes* OGN1 with *Dicentrarchus labrax* and *Sparus aurata* OGN1.